

GC-MS Profiling and Phytochemical Screening of Tanzania Orange (*Citrus Sinensis*) Peel of Essential Oils: Implication for Nutraceutical and Industrial Applications

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Abstract:

Citrus sinensis (sweet orange) peels, though commonly discarded as waste, contain valuable nutrients such as vitamin C, fiber, phenolics, and flavonoids justifying the need to convert this waste into beneficial products. The objective of this study was to assess the nutritional composition, phytochemical constituents, and essential oil profile of sweet orange peels to explore their potential applications. Methodologically, proximate analysis, elementary analysis, and qualitative phytochemical screening were conducted, alongside successive solvent extraction using hexane, ethyl acetate, and methanol to ensure comprehensive separation of phytochemicals; fresh peels were also subjected to steam distillation using TIRDO-fabricated equipment to obtain essential oils, which were analyzed through GC–MS. The results showed that the peels contained high protein (12.5%) and crude fiber (14.8%), making them suitable for incorporation into processed foods; phytochemical screening revealed the presence of multiple bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, glycosides, phenols, resins, saponins, steroids, tannins, terpenoids, and triterpenoids, with anthraquinones absent across all solvents. GC–MS analysis identified limonene (92.2%) as the major essential oil component, followed by myrcene (2.3%), sabinene (1.5%), linalool (1.4%), octanal (1.3%), α -pinene (0.6%), and trace amounts of decanal, α -terpineol, β -bisabolene (0.2%), and γ -terpinene (0.1%). In conclusion, the study demonstrates that sweet orange peels and their essential oils are promising sources of nutritionally and industrially valuable compounds suitable for edible medicinal use and diverse industrial applications.

Keywords: Essential Oil, *Citrus Sinensis*, Orange Peels, Phytochemical, Proximate Analysis.

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1. INTRODUCTION

An orange is a fruit of various citrus species in the family Rutaceae. It is primarily referred to as *Citrus sinensis*. Citrus (citrus spp) is one of the most abundant fruit crops, with world production estimated at 115 million tons per year. Citrus belongs to a large botanical family, where the sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) stands out as a major species. tangerines/mandarin (*Citrus reticulata*), lemon (*Citrus limon*), limes (several species), and grapefruits (*Citrus paradisi*). Citrus fruits are notable for their fragrance, partly due to flavonoids and limonoids in the rinds (Duarte et al 2016).

Citrus fruits and their by-products are of high economic and medicinal value because of their multiple uses in the food industry, cosmetics, and folk medicine (DAR, M.S. 2016.). The use of fruit peel extracts for antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Shehata *et al.*, 2021) can be of great significance in treatments of various ailments. Previous research revealed that extract from sweet orange peels had better antimicrobial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* and the dry ones are very strong against *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium notatum* (Oikeh *et al.*, 2020). *Citrus sinensis* peels are usually discarded as wastes; however, they are rich sources of Vitamin C, fibers, and many nutrients, including phenolics and flavonoids, which are also good antioxidants. Orange peels are rich in vitamins A and C, which are natural antioxidants that boost the overall health of the immune system and help fight infection, colds, and flu.

In large-scale consumption as fresh fruits, Citrus fruits are mainly processed to produce juice. Fruit by-products such as seeds, peels, stems, barks, and leaves have usually been discarded and are currently the cause of a serious disposal problem in food and agricultural industries. Peels are generated as the primary by-product, representing approximately 50–65 % of the fruit weight. The waste of the Citrus processing industry can be used as a potential source of valuable by-products (Ellouze et al 2022). Specifically, Citrus peels, commonly treated as agro-industrial waste, are a potential source of valuable secondary plant metabolites and essential oils (Duhan et al 2023). Therefore, there is a need to conduct extensive researches on the proper utilization of orange peel wastes and come up with useful products. This study examined the chemical composition and phytochemical screening of orange peels and their essential oils from Tanzania.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and processing of citrus *Sinensis* peels

Citrus sinensis peels were collected from the local market of Buguruni, Manzese, and Temeke, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. The peels were dried in a hybrid solar dryer for two to three days, depending on the weather. Peels of oranges were coarsely powdered using a mortar and pestle and were further reduced to powder using an electric blender.

Essential oil extraction

Fifteen kilograms (15 kg) of the well-crushed dry orange peels were fed into steam distillation equipment fabricated by the Tanzania Industrial Research and Development Organization (TIRDO) to obtain essential oils. The volume of essential oil extracted ranged between 1100 to 1200 ml.

Chemicals and reagents

The analytical reagents used during the conduction of this study included concentrated Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄), petroleum ether, Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), Boric acid solution, Anhydrous Sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄), Cupper sulfate (CuSO₄), distilled water, Hydrochloric acid (HCl), Wagner's reagent, Ferric chloride solution, Fehling's solution, Ethanol, Benzene, Ammonia solution, Methanol, Chloroform, Ethyl acetate, Tannic acid, Folin-Denis reagent, Sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃), Lead acetate, Baljet reagent and all other chemicals and reagents.

Proximate analysis

Determination of ash content

About 0.5 g samples orange peels were dried in the moisture extraction oven until constant weights were obtained. Then, the samples were transferred into the muffle furnace with a pair of tongs and ashed at 500 °C for 12 h until white ash was obtained. The samples were removed from the furnace and cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The percentage of total ash content of orange peels was calculated Eq 1

$$\text{Ash (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Determination of moisture content

Standard official methods of analysis of the AOAC (2010) were used for moisture content determination. 2 g of each orange peels sample was weighed into clean, dried, and pre-weighed crucibles. The orange peel samples were dried in the moisture extraction oven at 105 °C for 3 h. The dried samples were then removed from the oven, cooled in a desiccator and reweighed. The samples were again put back into the oven and dried until a constant weight was obtained. This analysis was carried out in triplicate and the average value was recorded as moisture content. In this regard, the weight of the empty dried dish was taken as W₁; the weight of 2 g samples with the dry dish was taken as W₂ and the sample was dried at 100 °C for 3 h and taken as W₃. The percentage moisture content was calculated by Eq.2: (2)

$$\% \text{Moisture} = \frac{(W_2 - W_3)}{W_2 - W_1}$$

Where, W₁ = Initial weight of empty crucible, W₂ = Weight of crucible + sample before drying, and W₃ = Final weight of crucible + sample after drying.

Determination of fiber content

2 g of orange peels sample were weighed; 200 mL of sulfuric acid was added to the boiling mixture and heated for 30 min, and filtered. After the residue was washed three times with hot water, 100 mL of 2 % NaOH was added to the boiling mixture and heated for 30 min, and filtered. Then, the filtrate washed carefully three times with hot water until it was free from the acid. The sample was dried under suction and transferred to an oven at 105 °C overnight, and finally weighed. The residue was ashed in a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 3 h till a light grey ash was formed, then weighed to a constant, and the total crude fiber percent was calculated by the Eq. 3:(3) Where: W_1 is the weight of sample before ignition, W_2 is weight of sample after ignition and W_3 is the original sample weight. Crude Fiber (%) = $((W_1 - W_2) / W_3) \times 100$

Determination of mineral content

Elements in orange peels were analyzed-using AAS technique except phosphorus and nitrogen. Phosphorous was determined by a colorimetric method (AOAC, 1994) and nitrogen by the Kjeldahl apparatus.

Determination of crude protein

The Kjeldahl method was used to determine the crude protein. About 5 g of orange peels sample was weighed with electrical balance and placed in digestion flask. A 2 g of Kjeldahl catalyst and 200 mL H_2SO_4 were added and boiled until the solution cooled and became clear. 60 mL H_2O and 6 drops of the mixed indicator were added and heated until all N_2 was distilled. Finally, the solution was titrated with NaOH and the crude protein content calculated Eq 4

$$\text{Crude protein (\%)} = (A - B * N * 14.007 * 6.250) / W$$

Where A is the volume (mL) of 0.25 N HCl used for sample titration, B is the volume (mL) of 0.25 N HCl used in blank titration, N is the normality of HCl, W is the weigh (g) of sample, 14.007 is the atomic weight of nitrogen, 6.25 is the protein- nitrogen conversation factor.

Determination of fat content

About 4 g of orange peels sample was weighed (w_1) and taken into Soxhlet; 250 mL of petroleum ether was added and heated at 85 °C until the solvent completely evaporated and assigned as w_2 . Then, the bottle containing the sample was cooled in desiccators and reweighed (w_3) and the fat content was calculated by Eqn5:

$$\text{Fat (\%)} = ((W_2 - W_1) / W_3) \times 100$$

Where: W_1 is the weight of empty bottle, W_2 is the weight of bottle and oil, W_3 is the weight of sample

Determination of carbohydrate

The percentage of carbohydrates in orange peels was calculated by using the following formula Eq 6

$$\text{Carbohydrate (\%)} = 100 - [\% \text{ moisture} + \% \text{ ash} + \% \text{ protein} + \% \text{ fat} + \% \text{ fibre}]$$

All tests were carried out in triplicates

Determination of minerals elements

The minerals were determined by dry ash extraction using the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric (AAS) technique (Shimadzu, AA-7000). All tests were carried out in duplicate.

Qualitative phytochemical screening

Qualitative assays for the presence of plant secondary metabolites such as reducing sugar, saponins, anthracene glycosides, deoxy sugar cardiac glycosides, tannins, flavonoids and alkaloids were carried out on the extract of the *Citrus sinensis* peels following standard procedure as described by Harbone (1998) and Sofowora (1993) All tests were carried out in triplicates.

Preparation of extracts

Aqueous and alcoholic extracts of orange peels were prepared by soaking 3.0 g of dried rind and 5.0 g of dried aril in 80 mL of distilled water separately for 24 hours, followed by filtration. Chloroform and petroleum ether extracts of orange peels were prepared by soaking 0.5 g of dried rind and 0.5 g of dried aril in 5 mL chloroform separately for 24 hours, followed by filtration.

Test for tannins

To 1 ml of extract, 2 ml of 5 % ferric chloride was added. The formation of dark blue or greenish black indicates the presence of tannins.

Test for saponins

2 ml of extract and 2 ml of distilled water were added and shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 min lengthwise. It resulted in the formation of a 1 cm layer of foam that indicated the presence of saponins.

Test for alkaloids

To 2 ml of extract, 2 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. Then, a few drops of Mayer's reagent were added. The presence of green color or white precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Test for flavonoids

To 2 ml of extract, 1 ml of 2 N sodium hydroxide was added. The presence of yellow color indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Test for glycosides

To 2 ml of extract, 3 ml of chloroform and 10 % ammonia solution was added. Formation of pink color indicates the presence of glycosides.

Test for phenols

2 ml of distilled water followed by a few drops of 10 % ferric chloride was added to 1 ml of the extract. The formation of blue or green colour indicates the presence of phenols.

Test for terpenoids

0.5 ml of the extract was treated with 2 ml of chloroform and conc. sulfuric acid. The formation of red-brown colour at the interface indicates the presence of terpenoids.

Test for cardiac glycosides

To 0.5 ml of the extract, 2 ml of glacial acetic acid and a few drops of ferric chloride were added. This was then layered with 1 ml of conc. sulfuric acid. The formation of a brown ring at the interface indicates the presence of cardiac glycosides.

Test for steroids

An equal volume of chloroform was added to 1 ml of fruit extract, and a few drops of concentrated sulfuric acid are added. The appearance of a brown ring indicates the presence of steroids, and the appearance of a bluish-brown ring indicates the presence of phytosterols.

Test for anthraquinones

0.5 g of the extract was boiled with 10 ml of sulfuric acid and filtered while hot. 5 ml of Chloroform was used to shake the filtrate. 1 ml of dilute ammonia was added to the chloroform layer. The resulting solution was then observed for a color change.

3. RESULTS

Proximate analysis of orange peels

The compositional content of protein, fat, carbohydrate, energy value, moisture and ash of orange peel are shown in Table 1. The moisture content of the dried powdered sample was found to be 9.1 ± 0.25 % w/w. Protein content was 12.5 ± 0.35 % w/w on dry weight basis (DW). Crude fat (6.9 ± 0.14 % w/w), fibre (14.8 ± 0.05 % w/w), ash (7.8 ± 0.15 % w/w) and the carbohydrate value was (48.6% w/w). The proximate analysis shows that the peels are a good source of protein (12.5 ± 0.35 % w/w). High moisture content promotes susceptibility to microbial activity. The orange peels contain appreciable amounts of fibre (14.8 ± 0.04 % w/w). The fibers and protein may be utilisable in food enrichment.

Table 1: Result of proximate analysis of orange peels

Sr. No	Proximate Analysis	% w/w Content
01	Moisture Content	9.1 ± 0.25
02	Ash Content	7.8 ± 0.15
03	Crude Protein	12.5 ± 0.35
04	Crude Fat	6.9 ± 0.14
05	Crude Fiber	14.8 ± 0.04
06	Carbohydrate Content	48.6

Minerals content of orange peels

The data presented in Table 2 show the mineral content of orange peels. Calcium, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, sodium, manganese, copper, zinc, and iron were detected. The results also indicated higher amount of calcium and potassium content in orange peels (150 and 320 mg/100 g respectively) followed by nitrogen (228 mg/100 g). However, sodium and phosphorus content was found in moderate amounts (55.6 and 50.2 mg/100g respectively) and iron (9.4). The composition of Cu, Mn and Zn were 3.46, 0.43 and 0.29 mg/100 g respectively.

Table 2: Minerals content (mg/100g) of orange peels (mg/100 g)

K	Ca	Na	N	P	Fe	Cu	Mn	Zn
320	150	55.6	228	50.2	9.49	3.46	0.43	0.29

This study revealed that orange peels contain useful elements required by human body such as calcium, iron, potassium, zinc, and manganese. Nutritional assessment is important in every patient. Malnutrition is a common problem worldwide, and in developed in countries. Various studies have shown that patients may have evidence, not only of protein-calorie malnutrition, but also of vitamin and mineral deficiencies, especially after major surgery or chronic illness. Iron is an essential element in humans, being the central ion in hemoglobin. Iron deficiency causes a failure of hemoglobin synthesis, leading to anemia (Itrat et al 2025). Calcium is essential for growing and keeping your bones strong. It's also an essential nutrient for healthy cell function. Your body needs calcium to support muscle and nerve function, regulate blood pressure and hormone levels, as well as help with communication between cells (Goudarzi et al 2018). Potassium plays a critical role in human health. It is involved in maintaining blood pressure and reducing risk of stroke, preserving calcium stores in bone and helping the kidneys work efficiently and it is important for maintaining fluid and electrolyte balance. It also helps move nutrients into cells and waste products out of cells (Kieneker 2014; Willey et al., 2017; Newberry et al., 2018). Zinc is an essential element present in over 200 metalloproteins as it is required for the synthesis of protein and collagen, thus contributing to wound healing and a healthy skin. Zinc deficiency causes characteristic skin rash and hair loss,

wound breakdown and delayed healing (Chasapis et al 2020). Phosphorus contributes in bone formation, energy metabolism and nucleic acid metabolism. (Calvo et al 2014). Manganese helps the body to form connective tissue, bones, blood clotting factors, and sex hormones. It also plays a role in fat and carbohydrate metabolism, calcium absorption, and blood sugar regulation. Manganese is also necessary for normal brain and nerve function. (Horning et al 2015).

Qualitative phytochemical screening of the orange peels

The phytochemical analysis of various extracts of *Citrus sinensis* peels is shown in the Table 3 and Table 4. It was observed that; the *Citrus sinensis* peels of different extracts indicated the presence of alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, glycoside, phenols, resins, saponins, steroids, tannins, terpenoids and triterpenoids. Surprisingly, anthraquinone was not observed in any of the extracts. However, flavonoids were present in three extracts of methanol, aqueous and ethyl acetate, alkaloids were found in methanol, aqueous and chloroform extract, cardiac glycosides were present in methanol, aqueous and petroleum ether extracts, glycoside was found in methanol, and ethyl acetate while saponin was presents in only methanol and chloroform extracts. Steroids and triterpenoids were present in methanol and aqueous, tannin was presented in methanol and petroleum ether extracts, terpenoids was present in methanol, aqueous and petroleum ether extracts.

Table 3: Qualitative phytochemical screening of the orange peels in aqueous and alcoholic extracts

Plant Extracts	Water	Methanol	Ethyl Acetate
Alkaloids	+	+++	-
Anthraquinones	-	-	-
Cardiac glycosides	+	+	
Flavonoids	+++	+++	+
Glycosides	-	+++	+
Phenols	-	+++	-
Resins	+	+	+
Saponins	-	+++	-
Steroids	++	+++	-
Tannins	-	+++	-
Terpenoids	++	+++	-
Triterpenoids	++	+	-

Note: +++: highly present, ++: moderately present, +: Low, -: absent.

Table 4: Qualitative phytochemical screening of the orange peels in petroleum ether and chloroform extracts

Plant Extracts	Petroleum Ether	Chloroform
Alkaloids	-	+
Anthraquinones	-	-
Cardiac glycosides	+	-
Flavonoids	-	-
Glycosides	-	-
Phenols	-	-
Resins	-	+
Saponins	-	+
Steroids	-	-
Tannins	+	-
Terpenoids	-	+
Triterpenoids	-	-

Note +++: highly present, ++: moderately present, +: Low, -: absent.

While phenols were found only in two extracts; methanol and aqueous extract, resins were absent in only Petroleum ether extracts. The study revealed that methanolic fruit peels extract was found to have more constituents when compared with other extracts followed by aqueous extracts.

Citrus Sinensis is a rich source of secondary metabolites which contribute to the pharmacological activities attributed to this plant. Phytochemical screening revealed that flavonoids were dominant in many extracts of *Citrus sinensis* peel. Citrus plants could be regarded as medicinal due to the high level of flavonoid content in them. Flavonoids possess a number of medicinal benefits, including anticancer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antiviral properties. They also have neuro-protective and cardio-protective. These biological activities depend upon the type of flavonoid, its (possible) mode of action, and its bioavailability (Ullah, 2020). Natural products have been and will be important sources of new pharmaceutical compounds. Recently, there has been a renewed interest in natural product research due to the failure of alternative drug discovery methods to deliver many lead compounds in key therapeutic areas. In this sense, considering the health benefits of *C. sinensis* presents excellent options for treating or helping in a disease due to its bioactive compounds (drug candidates) that show important activities or for developing new products.

Essential oil

Essential oil extraction from 15,000 g of *Citrus sinensis* peels was carried out using water steam distillation, yielding 1,200 g (8%) of essential oil. The obtained oil exhibited a clear appearance with an orange-yellow color and a characteristic sweet, fruity orange-peel

aroma. The extraction yield was calculated as the percentage of the essential oil weight relative to the initial peel weight, as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: extraction yield

Species name	Orange peels weight (g)	Essential oil weight (g)	Yield (%)
	15000	1200	8

Chemical composition of the essential oil of *Citrus sinensis*

The chemical composition of the essential oil of *Citrus sinensis* is presented in Table 6. The result showed the presence of the following compounds; limonene; 92.2 %, myrcene; 2.3 %, Sabinene 1.5 %, linalool; 1.4 %, octanal; 1.3 %, α -pinene; 0.6 %, decanal, α -Terpineol and β -Bisabolene were 0.2 %, and gamma-Terpinene 0.1 %.

Table 6: Chemical composition of *Citrus sinensis* (sweet orange) essential oil.

S/n	Name of compound	Concentration of volatile compound (%)
1	α -Pinene	0.6
2	Limonene	92.2
3	Linalool	1.4
4	beta-Myrcene	2.3
5	gamma-Terpinene	0.1
6	Sabinene	1.5
7	Decanal	0.2
8	Octanal	1.3
9	α -Terpineol	0.2
10	β -Bisabolene	0.2

Citrus essential oils are characterized by a volatile and a non-volatile fraction. The volatile fraction is mainly composed of monoterpene and sesquiterpene hydrocarbons, also by their oxygenated derivatives, aliphatic aldehydes, alcohols and esters, forming until 99 % of the essential oil. The non-volatile fraction could contain hydrocarbons, sterols, fatty acids, waxes, carotenoids, coumarins, psoralens, and flavonoids (Zoccali et al 2018). Terpenes, the main components of essential oil, are produced by various species of plants and perform diverse functions, such as defence mechanisms against herbivores and pathogens and plant developmental physiology. The terpene basic chemical structure consists of an isoprene unit (Mewalal *et al.*, 2017). Terpenes are employed in disease prevention and treatment, offering various biological effects such as antimicrobial, anti-allergenic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties (Rufino *et al.*, 2015). Limonene is one of the most common terpenes in nature and a major constituent of citrus essential oils. The results in Table 6 confirmed that limonene was the main compound present (92.2 %) in the essential oil of *Citrus sinensis*. The therapeutic

effects of limonene have been extensively studied, proving anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antinociceptive, anticancer, antidiabetic, antihyperalgesic, antiviral, and gastroprotective effects, among other beneficial effects in health (Vieira et al, 2018).

4. CONCLUSION

Proximate analysis of the orange peels showed that they contain appreciable amounts of fiber implying that the orange peel is a source of important nutrients. Also, the peels of the orange, contain useful elements required by the human body including calcium, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, sodium, manganese, copper, zinc and iron. On the other hand, *Citrus sinensis* essential oils, obtained from steam distillation contains various compounds, with limonene; occupying the largest amount (92.2 %).

The results of the present study demonstrated that the orange peels and essential oil investigated are potential sources of valuable compounds that might be utilized for edible, medicinal, and other industrial applications. The findings reveal that orange peels are rich in vitamins A and C, both of which are natural antioxidants that boost the overall health of the immune system and help fight infections, colds, and flu.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no any conflicts of interest.

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